

Study Material Summary

Fuzzing Inference-Time Privacy Risks in Deployed Large Language Models

1. Oracle Definitions
2. Risk 1: Prompt Category Templates
 - Authority
 - Benign
 - Confidential
 - Distractor
 - Exfiltrate
 - Social Engineering
 - Task
3. Canary Values Dataset
4. Base Seeds Dataset
5. Risk-Specific Transformations
6. Experimental Results
7. Risk 2: Re-identification of De-identified Information
 - `authorship.yaml`
 - `law_policy.yaml`

- learning_platform.yaml
- mobility.yaml
- research.yaml
- volunteer.yaml

8. Evaluated Models

- DeepSeek-Chat V3.2
- OpenAI GPT-5.2
- Gemini 3 Flash